

LEVEL OF COMPETENCE AND PERFORMANCE OF NON-TEACHING PERSONNEL IN THE CITY DIVISION OF ILAGAN: A BASIS FOR AN UPSKILLING PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the competence and performance of non-teaching personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan as a basis for developing an upskilling program. The research employed a descriptive-inferential design, surveying 104 administrative employees. The study examined respondents' profiles, including sex, age, position, and educational attainment, and measured their competence in areas such as self-management, professionalism, ethics, and teamwork. Performance was evaluated based on Key Result Areas (KRAs) from their Individual Performance Commitment Review Forms. Findings revealed that the non-teaching personnel were highly competent and performed outstandingly, with some variation based on profile variables. The study identified a significant relationship between competence and performance, emphasizing the need for a sustainable upskilling program to maintain and enhance employee competence and performance. Recommendations include developing an appraisal system, increasing training opportunities, and implementing a tailored upskilling program.

Keywords: *Non-Teaching Personnel, Competence, Performance, Upskilling Program, Schools Division of the City of Ilagan*

INTRODUCTION

In the realm of public service and continuous improvement, non-teaching personnel have been involved in the mandate of quality, standard, and sustainable service for every Filipino. In the Department of Education, public service is attributed to the alignment of its mandate to educational goals and objectives. In lieu of this, administrative employees make huge contributions in the attainment of its lifetime goals.

As immersed in this field, the growing demands for continuous educational and professional growth and development ignited the spirit to alleviate conventional approaches in the service which are no longer applicable in the modern and changing times. Instead, an upskilling program that would cater to the needs, skills, competencies, and performance of every non-teaching employee is necessary to effectuate improved and innovative delivery of public service. This demand has led towards improvements in the education sector and school organizations where services are provided, and employees are trained to effectively deliver quality public services.

Including non-teaching staff members in the upskilling strategy may have the potential for improving school culture by galvanizing shared beliefs, attitudes, and practices amongst staff members, increasing employee engagement by communicating clear expectations and purpose in job responsibilities, promoting quality in the work environment through a cohesive organizational structure.

The non-teaching staff includes those individuals who are not immediate part-takes in a classroom for teaching but still play crucial roles in supporting the school system and its various functions. Their responsibilities range from administration and finance to maintenance and student support. According to Department of Education Memorandum No. 007 s. 2023, non-teaching position refers to a position whose primary duties and responsibilities contribute to the delivery of basic education services and achievement of agency outcomes, but do not involve nor directly support the actual conduct of teaching or delivery of instruction.

As Wanjiku (2021) mentioned that upskilling program represents a carefully designed plan to guide the actions and relationships of organizational members to achieve shared goals. In education, strategy affects policies, procedures, and the roles of every stakeholder, to have a positive impact on organizational achievement. Hence, demands for higher standards in education in recent decades have led to upskilling programs aimed at increasing accountability for administrators and non-teaching personnel to aid the current situations of organizational and institutional development. The Department of Education adopts mechanisms and programs to include non-teaching personnel through its mandate to elevate standards in the delivery of services.

Despite the importance and incorporation of staff development in basic education, there is limited research on the availability and use of learning opportunities for non-teaching personnel in the form of professional development. Without professional

development, upskilling programs, and engagement opportunities, non-teaching personnel lack visibility, disengage, and ultimately may separate from institutions of basic education. Deliberate organizational efforts to provide access to new learning opportunities and promote personal growth among non-teaching personnel is the development and institutionalization of centers for professional development, also called staff development centers, and staff training and professional development centers including upskilling programs.

In the study by Franks (2017), non-teaching personnel are integral to student success and educational development. Some non-teaching personnel help the schools' direction through administration and capability building towards an effective public institution and organization towards dispensing of public duties. Goot (2017), reinforced the importance of how non-teaching personnel influence an agency's overall development. In addition to serving as development navigators and helping the trajectory of most educational organizations, non-teaching personnel maintain campus operations so students can focus on learning, and teachers can focus on teaching. Thus, their engagement, professional development, and personal growth are instrumental to the functioning of higher education.

Initially, professional development aimed to improve employee performance deficiencies as mentioned by Rebores (2019). However, professional development has become a significant factor in connecting employees to their workplace and promoting group cohesiveness and a sense of community. Employee well-being, high employee engagement, and professional development are connected and correlate with organizational social capital. Hence, there is a need to navigate through the competencies of non-teaching personnel by providing an upskilling program to explore and catapult the road for educational development as drivers of leadership, administration, and internal and external processes. Organizational development is the key factor toward the effective delivery of services and duties and responsibilities toward the public good. Most organizations implement organizational and systemic mechanisms for the development of their employees in terms of personal and professional aspects and the improvement of the organization or agency.

Despite the number of research investigating the impact of training and upskilling on the performance of employees and in identifying the competencies of non-teaching personnel, few studies have tackled the issue at educational institutions involving non-teaching personnel, which are specific governmental agencies and organizations. In the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, training development of teaching and non-teaching personnel has been an upward trend to navigate its employees' personal and professional efficacy. However, the question of the impact of training on the personal and professional development of non-teaching personnel has undeniably placed administrative improvement upon the extent of training improvement. The transformation of training into productivity and organizational development leads to numerous concerns about its alignment with the relevance and significance of such training.

Therefore, it is vital to understand the role of professional development and upskilling programs in shaping professional development experiences and employee engagement among non-teaching personnel. As immersed in the administrative works, the researcher is imbued with great fidelity to the thrusts and principles of this study as it manifestly implores work experiences and duties prescribed by the Department. In lieu of this, the role of non-teaching personnel is further enhanced upon technical assistance and other improvements provided by the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan. Hence, the necessity augments for a developmental and innovative upskilling program to address such work demands arising from the workplace.

This study examined the role of a specific type of non-teaching staff for a school's division and school organization, intending to promote and establish an improved upskilling program for the role of these valuable employees. This study aimed to identify and improve the competencies of non-teaching employees of elementary schools, secondary schools, and offices in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan towards devising an upskilling program.

Conceptual Framework

The determination of the competencies of non-teaching personnel is an integral process of educational organizations' development as well as with the internal and external administrative processes of a school's division office. This study was anchored from the Strategic Performance Management System of the Civil Service Commission of the Philippines.

The Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) is a mechanism that links employee performance with organizational performance to enhance the performance orientation of the compensation system. It ensures that the employee achieves the objectives set by the organization and the organization, on the other hand, achieves the objectives that it has set as its strategic plan.

The SPMS Objectives are: (a) to concretize the linkage of organizational performance with the Philippine Development Plan, Agency Strategic Plan, and Organizational Performance Indicator Framework OPIF; (b) to ensure organizational and individual effectiveness by cascading institutional accountabilities to the various levels of the organization; and (c) to link performance management with other HR systems.

The SPMS has the following basic elements: a) Goals that are aligned to agency mandate and organizational priorities; b) System that is outputs/outcomes-oriented; c) A team approach to performance management; d) Forms that are user-friendly and shows alignment of individual and organizational goals; e) Information systems that support monitoring and evaluation; and f) A Communication plan.

More importantly, the SPMS complements the Results-Based Performance Management System that is implemented by the Office of the President and that links organizational performance to societal goals. Just like the teaching personnel, non-

teaching personnel also have competencies that are anchored from the job descriptions according to their positions and described by their Key Result Areas or KRAs. The RPMS was designed with the intent of improving teacher quality. It aims to align performance targets and accomplishments with the PPST. In RPMS, teachers are provided with Key Result Areas (KRA), which are the general outputs or outcomes that are expected of them.

The past performance evaluation and appraisal systems that CSC implemented over the years have largely focused only on individual appraisals, which were used for personnel actions such as incentives, promotion, and separation. However, they have not shown how employee performance has contributed to or hindered organizational effectiveness. To address the gaps and weaknesses found in previous evaluation systems, the CSC recently introduced the Strategic Performance Management System (SPMS) after its pilot test in 2011. The SPMS incorporates the positive features of past initiatives. Like its predecessor, PMS-OPES, the SPMS seeks to link individual performance with the agency's organizational vision, mission, and strategic goals. With some adjustments, it also makes use of existing performance evaluation and management systems and links performance management with other human resource (HR) systems.

The study made use of the Input-Process-Output type. The input box in Figure 1 consists of the non-teaching personnel's profile including sex, age, position/designation, type of school/office assignment, highest educational attainment, and relevant trainings attended for the last three years. The input box also includes the Level of Competence of Non-Teaching Personnel in terms of Self-Management; Professionalism and Ethics; Result Focus, Teamwork; Service Orientation; and Innovation. Finally, it also includes the Level of Performance of Non-Teaching Personnel based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual/Office Performance Commitment Review Form.

The process box reflects the process phase which includes the analyses of the variables including respondents' profiles, the level of competence of non-teaching personnel, and the level of performance of non-teaching personnel based on the Key Result Areas. Finally, the output box contains the Level of Competence and Level of Performance of Non-Teaching Personnel as a basis for an upskilling program.

Figure 1. The Input-Process-Output Model of the Study

Research Questions

The study aimed to identify and determine the competencies of non-teaching personnel in the City Division of Ilagan as a basis for an upskilling program. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - a. Sex;
 - b. Age;
 - c. Position/Designation;
 - d. Type of School/Office Assignment;

- e. Highest Educational Attainment; and
 - f. Relevant Trainings Attended (for last three years)
 2. How competent are the Non-Teaching Personnel in the City Division of Ilagan in terms of the following:
 - a. Self-Management;
 - b. Professionalism and Ethics;
 - c. Result Focus
 - d. Teamwork;
 - e. Service Orientation;
 - f. Innovation.
 3. Is there a significant difference in the level of competence of the respondents when grouped according to their profile?
 4. What is the level of performance of Non-Teaching Personnel based on the Key Result Areas (KRAs)?
 5. Is there a significant difference in the level of Performance of Non-Teaching Personnel in terms of Key Result Areas (KRAs) when grouped according to profile?
 6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of competencies and the level of performance of the Non-Teaching Personnel?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive inferential research design. This provides an accurate and valid presentation of the factors or variables that pertain to research questions. This study described the competencies of non-teaching personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan and its impact on the personal and professional skills development and efficacy of non-teaching personnel as a basis for an upskilling program, thus the descriptive method is appropriate for this research since this method is used for gathering current conditions.

The correlational approach was further utilized to gauge relationships between the described and identified research variables. In this study, the correlational approach was used to test the relationship between the level of competencies and the level of performance of the Non-Teaching Personnel. Moreover, a significant difference was tested between and among variables including the profile of the respondents, competencies, and performance of the respondents using their performance rating from the Key Result Areas in their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form.

Locale of the Study

This research work was conducted in the public elementary and secondary schools including the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan. The City of Ilagan is mainly composed of rural areas interconnected by rivers as the main body

of water in the city. The rural areas compose the most parts of the city including the elementary schools, integrated schools, and secondary schools where the non-teaching personnel are deployed. On the other hand, the urban areas are home to the biggest secondary and elementary schools in the Division, the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan is also located adjacent to the biggest secondary school in the City of Ilagan – the Isabela National High School. Some schools in the urban areas also compose most of the employees and non-teaching personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan. The maps presented below are the geographical classifications of the rural and urban areas of the City of Ilagan.

Selection and Description of the Respondents

The study included the entire population of non-teaching personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan as respondents in the study.

The respondents were composed of Administrative Officers, Administrative Assistants, Administrative Aides, Accountants, and Budget Officers employed in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan and deployed in different schools and the offices of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan. Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents by school and administrative offices in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan.

Table 1. Description of Respondents in the Study

TYPE OF SCHOOL/ OFFICE	DESCRIPTION OF RESPONDENTS IN THE STUDY												
	AA IV	AA VI	ADAS I	ADAS II	ADAS III	AO I	AO II	AO IV	AO V	AC CT. I	AC CT. III	B.O . I	TOTAL
Elementary				7	9		26						42
Secondary	7	1		11		1	1			1			22
Senior High School				1	5		1						7
Division Office	1	2	3	3	6		11	4	1		1	1	33
TOTAL	8	3	3	22	20	1	39	4	1	1	1	1	104

Data Gathering Instruments

Survey-Questionnaire. This research employed a survey questionnaire as the main type of research instrument. The questionnaire elicited the competence of non-teaching personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan as a basis for an upskilling program. The survey questionnaire was adapted from the Core Behavioral Competencies of the Individual/Office Performance Commitment Review Form of the respondents. In

addition, the performance level part of the questionnaire was derived from their Individual/Office Performance Commitment Review Form.

The first part of the survey questionnaire composes the profile of the respondents including sex, age, position/designation, type of school/ office assignment, highest educational attainment, and relevant trainings attended in the last three years.

The second part of the questionnaire includes the following areas of competence of non-teaching personnel: Self-Management, Professionalism and Ethics, Result Focus, Teamwork, Service Orientation & Innovation. The items of competencies were derived from the Core Behavioral Competencies of the Individual/Office Performance Commitment Review Form – Result-Based Performance Management System of Non-Teaching Personnel of the Department of Education. This part is scored through a four-point Likert Scale.

Finally, the third part of the survey questionnaire elicits the respondents' performance based on KRAs (Key Result Areas). This data was gathered through the face-to-face method of data gathering. Further, the respondents' performance was based on documentary analysis and interviews.

Interview Guide. The interview procedure was conducted along with the floating of the questionnaire to the respondents. Aside from the survey questionnaire, respondents were interviewed using a non-structured interview guide.

Documentary Analysis. Documentary analysis was also conducted in the determination of common and specific responses of the respondents in their performance ratings. This was done by looking at and assessing their personal and individual files (IPCRF/OPCRF) to match the data needed for the whole conduct of the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

To conduct the research study, a letter of permission was sought from the office of the City Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher did the floating of the questionnaire through personal delivery to the respective schools or workplace assignments of the respondents. To ensure 100 percent retrieval of the questionnaire, the researcher carefully supervised the data collection.

In compliance with the Data Privacy Act, the researcher first sought the approval of the respondents and was constantly informed that the data and information to be gathered from the respondents were treated with utmost confidentiality. The gathered data were recorded, organized, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly.

Finally, the researcher also sought and requested the copies of respondents' Individual or Office Performance Commitment Review Form from the Human Resources Development Office for validation and verification purposes.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical tools utilized in treating data to be gathered included the following:

1. For the first profile of the respondents, descriptive statistics such as frequency count and percentage were used to treat the variables;
2. In identifying the levels of competence and performance of the respondents based on their KRAs, the weighted mean was utilized;
3. Inferential statistics including the One-Way ANOVA were used to test the significant difference between and among the identified variables in the study; and
4. Pearson- r was further used to identify the relationship between and among the variables.

Data Analysis Procedure

To determine the level of competence of non-teaching personnel from the subparts of the survey questionnaire, the following was used:

Interpretation of the Level of Competence

Point	Scale	Qualitative Description
4	3.25 – 4.00	Highly Competent
3	2.50 – 3.24	Competent
2	1.75 – 2.49	Fairly Competent
1	1.00 – 1.74	Not Competent

To determine the level of performance of non-teaching personnel, the following interpretation of the 5-point scale was utilized:

Interpretation of the Level of Performance

Point	Scale	Qualitative Description
5	4.50 – 5.00	Outstanding
4	3.50 – 4.49	Very Satisfactory
3	2.50 – 3.49	Satisfactory
2	1.50 – 2.49	Unsatisfactory
1	below – 1.49	Poor

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	33	31.73
Female	71	68.27

Total	104	100.0
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Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to their sex. From the data presented, it could be gleaned that most of the respondents are female with 71 or 68.27 percent while only 33 or 31.73 percent male respondents.

This means that there are more female administrative and non-teaching employees in the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan than male employees. This is evident in the distribution of respondents in schools and offices and departments of the Schools Division Office. As affirmed in the study of Jeremiah, et. al (2014), there are more women in the administrative field than men who dominate other fields such as engineering and sciences. Here, as concluded by Franks (2017) administrative duties and responsibilities are often disposed of and deployed to women employees who correspond to the requirements, qualifications, and other educational requisites of the specific administrative jobs. Hence, institutions with huge and established administrative offices hire more women applicants who satisfy the required competencies.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20 – 25 Years Old	3	2.88
26 – 30 Years Old	31	29.81
31 – 35 Years Old	30	28.85
36 – 40 Years Old	14	13.46
41 – onwards	26	25.00
Total	104	100.0

Table 3 shows the distribution of frequency and percentage of the respondents in terms of their age range. From the data presented, it reveals that most of the respondents with 31 or 29.81 percent responses belong to the age group between 26 to 30 years old. Moreover, there are 30 or 28.85 percent of respondents belong to the age group between 31 – 35 years old, 14 or 13.46 percent of respondents who belong to the 36 – 40 years old age group, and 26 or 25 percent of respondents who are categorized under 41 years old and above.

Meanwhile, there are only three 2.88 percent of respondents who belong to the age group from 20 to 25 years old. This means that there are only a few fresh graduates who belong to the latter age group who are employed in administrative positions and designations in schools and offices of the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan. As emphasized by Mercado (2023), this age group characterizes a large volume of younger employees who seek to establish themselves in the administrative workplace.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Position/Designation

Position/Designation	Frequency	Percentage
Administrative Aide IV	8	7.69
Administrative Aide VI	3	2.88
Administrative Assistant I	3	2.88
Administrative Assistant II	22	21.15
Administrative Assistant III	20	19.23
Administrative Officer I	1	0.96
Administrative Officer II	39	37.5
Administrative Officer III	0	0.00
Administrative Officer IV	4	3.85
Administrative Officer V	1	0.96
Accountant I	1	0.96
Accountant II	0	0.00
Accountant III	1	0.96
Budget Officer III	1	0.96
Total	104	100.0

The table above enshrines the distribution of frequency and percentage of the respondent's position or designation as non-teaching personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan.

Of all the respondents, most of them hold the position of Administrative Officer II with 39 or 37.5 percent. There are 22 or 21.15 percent of the respondents hold the position of Administrative Assistant II. Twenty or 19.23 percent of the respondents are employed as Administrative Assistant III. There are eight or 7.69 percent of the respondents hold the position of Administrative Aide IV, and 4 or 3.85 respondents are employed as Administrative Officer IV Three or 2.88 percent of the respondents hold the position of Administrative Aide VI.

In the position of Administrative Assistants, there are only 3 or 2.88 percent of respondents who are employed as Administrative Assistant I. For the Administrative Officer position, Administrative Officer I is reserved for only one or 0.96 percent of respondents the same as Administrative Officer V, Accountant I, Accountant III, Budget Officer III.

Finally, there are only three employees who are employed in the accounting department of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan who hold the positions of Accountant I, Accountant III, and Budget Officer III. As per DepEd Memorandum Order No. 35 s. 2017, these positions are tasked to manage and supervise the finances, accounting, and other related management schemes of the Schools Division Office relative to their job descriptions.

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to the Type of School/Office Assignment

Type of School/Office Assignment	Frequency	Percentage
Small School	30	28.85
Medium School	21	20.19
Large School	29	27.88
Division Office	24	23.08
Total	104	100.0

The table above shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to the type of school or assignment. It is revealed that 30 or 28.85 percent of respondents are deployed in small schools. These schools are mainly elementary schools which are distributed in almost every barangay of the City of Ilagan. Twenty-nine or 27.88 percent of non-teaching personnel who are deployed in the large school category. These schools are composed of national high schools, central schools, and large integrated schools that cater to the complete basic education system. In medium schools which are some of the elementary schools and integrated schools in the City Division of Ilagan, there are 21 or 20.19 percent non-teaching personnel deployed in these schools.

On the other hand, there are 24 or 23.08 percent non-teaching personnel deployed in the Schools Division Office. As per DepEd Memorandum Order No. 35 s. 2017, these non-teaching personnel are delegated to the offices and departments of the Schools Division Office which include the Human Resources Office, Accounting Office, and other administrative departments.

Table 6. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
College Graduate	67	64.42
Master's Degree	35	33.65
Doctor's Degree	2	1.92
Total	104	100.0

Table 6 represents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of their highest educational attainment. The data reveals that 67 or 64.42 percent of respondents are college graduates, while 35 or 33.65 percent of respondents have master's degrees. However, only 2 or 1.92 percent of respondents are doctorate holders.

The data implies that most respondents only attended bachelor's education as their highest educational attainment which signifies that no other further continuing professional education or degree was finished. This further signifies that there is a need for further educational development programs for non-teaching personnel to cope with the demands of educational requirements for further or higher administrative positions with accompanied tasks, duties, and responsibilities.

As discussed under the Civil Service Commission – Competency-Based Recruitment and Qualifications Standards, employees of the government with the main duties of governmental and public service in nature are required to uphold the requirements set forth by the commission which includes the combination and cumulative possession of eligibility, education, training, experience, and competencies. In the education requirement, employees must possess the minimum educational qualifications relative to the position or office to be taken. Further, the higher the public office sought, the higher the educational qualification required.

Table 7. Frequency and Rank Distribution of the Respondents According to Relevant Trainings Attended in the Last 3 Years

Relevant Trainings Attended in the Last 3 Years	Frequency	Rank
Finance Management and Budget Related	75	1
Administrative and Technical Support	54	2
Accounting and Auditing Services	41	3
Human Resources and Personnel Management	40	4
Property and Resources Custodianship	28	5
Records and Files Management	32	6
Coordination, Communication, and	18	7
Organizational Support	15	8

The table above reflects the frequency and ranking of the relevant training courses for the last three years attended by the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan.

From the data presented, it can be gleaned that the field of Finance Management and Budget Related is the most attended training course attended by the respondents with 75 respondents who are engaged in the said training course. This field is not limited to training in financial management, budget allocation and appropriation, school financial status, and other rules and promulgations relevant to financial management.

The second most attended training course is Administrative and Technical Support with 54 respondents who are engaged in the said course. This training course offers several aspects including the provision of aid and information, civil service procedures, requirements, qualifications for hiring and promotion, and other administrative and technical support for papers and procedures. The third most attended training course is Accounting and Auditing Services with 41 respondents. This is mostly common to accountants and administrative officers and assistants with similar duties and responsibilities in school and office accounting and auditing.

Meanwhile, 40 respondents attended course trainings in the field of Human Resources and Personnel Management. This is usually attended by administrative officers and administrative assistants. 32 respondents are engaged in attending training courses relating to Records and Files Management which are fundamentally one of the

main duties and responsibilities of administrative officers, administrative aides, and administrative assistants.

Moreover, the last three training courses that the respondents attended for the last years are training courses in Property and Resources Custodianship with 28 respondents, Coordination and Communication with 18 respondents, and Organizational Support with 15 respondents.

The training of non-teaching staff in experiential higher education institutions makes it possible to act with a certain meaning in certain situations. This allows for greater direct contact, strengthens the relationship between the individual and the object, and supports reflection and recall of experiences as provided by the Civil Service Commission. Further, as emphasized by Bilhim (2019), it is in this context that the exchange of experiences and comparisons of methods and results becomes relevant, creating space for collective work. It is a return to experience that enables transformation into formal knowledge, where the presence of partners translates into social interventions, essential for experiential knowledge to grow. The development of Human Resource Management, seen as a strategic factor, is the phase where we see changes in human resource management developed through administrative techniques, where there is a department of people to maintain only a predetermined order, for management based on the competitive advantage that is achieved by the factors people in the company.

Further, these descriptions for further training are enhanced and sought to be established by the PRIME-HRM of the Civil Service Commission. The Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management (PRIME-HRM) integrates and enhances the Personnel Management Assessment and Assistance Program (PMAAP) and the CSC Agency Accreditation Program (CSCAAP). It is a mechanism that empowers government agencies by developing their human resource management competencies, systems, and practices toward HR excellence. PRIME-HRM entails greater engagement not just of the human resource management officer (HRMO) but also of the officials and the rank-and-file employees of the agency.

Level of Competence of the Non-Teaching Personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan

Table 8. Level of Competence of the Non-Teaching Personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan in Terms of Self-Management

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Set personal goals and direction, needs and development.	3.58	Highly Competent
2. Undertake personal actions and behaviors that are clear and purposive and take into account personal goals and values congruent to those of the organization.	3.53	Highly Competent
3. Display emotional maturity and enthusiasm for and is challenged by higher goals.	3.52	Highly Competent

4. Prioritize work tasks and schedules (through Gantt charts, checklists, etc.) to achieve goals.	3.57	Highly Competent
5. Set high-quality, challenging, realistic goals for self and others.	3.54	Highly Competent
Average Weighted Mean	3.55	Highly Competent

Table 8 shows the level of competence of the non-teaching personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan in terms of Self-Management.

As presented above, respondents under this indicator of competence obtained an average weighted mean of 3.55 which means that the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan are highly competent. Further, this implies that employees possess features and administrative prowess that qualify them to exhibit a sense of self-organization and self-management. Self-management allows employees to control and handle emotions and other personal circumstances that enable them to produce quality and standard results in their workstations.

In this indicator, Item 1 had the highest weighted mean of 3.58 which categorically implies that respondents set personal goals and direction, needs and development. This aspect manifests respondents' ability to zeal personal and professional goals and direction for further growth and development as members of an organizational institution. Item 3, on the other hand, obtained a weighted mean of 3.52 which means that the respondents are still highly competent in displaying emotional maturity and enthusiasm for and are challenged by higher goals.

As affirmed by Bakker (2017), competence goes higher when employees share their values and personal goals in an organization. When shared values become embedded within an organization, they form the foundation of the organizational culture. When engaged, employees feel compelled to strive towards a challenging goal. Engaged employees become absorbed in their work, experiencing a flow in which they lose track of time and diminish their response to distractions.

Table 9. Level of Competence of Non-Teaching Personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan in Terms of Professionalism and Ethics

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Demonstrate the values and behavior enshrined in the Norms of Conduct and Ethical Standards for public officials and employees (RA 6713).	3.62	Highly Competent
2. Practice ethical and professional behavior and conduct taking into account the impact of his/her actions and decisions.	3.64	Highly Competent
3. Maintain a professional image: being trustworthy, regularity of attendance and	3.63	Highly Competent

punctuality, good grooming and communication.		
4. Make personal sacrifices to meet the organization's needs.	3.58	Highly Competent
5. Act with a sense of urgency and responsibility to meet the organization's needs, improve systems, and help others improve their effectiveness.	3.60	Highly Competent
Average Weighted Mean	3.61	Highly Competent

Table 9 indicates the level of competence of the non-teaching personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan in terms of Professionalism and Ethics.

It can be gleaned from the table shown above that the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan are highly competent in terms of professionalism and ethics with an average weighted mean of 3.61. This signifies that these employees demonstrate attributes and features expected from a government employee in accordance with rules, regulations, and policies set forth by the State including the Civil Service Rules for government employees, and other relevant laws regulating the conduct of public employees in the public service.

Furthermore, Item 2 obtained the highest weighted mean in this indicator which means that the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan are highly competent in the practice of ethical and professional behavior and conduct considering the impact of their actions and decisions. On the other hand, Item 4 obtained a weighted mean of 3.58 which implies that respondents are highly competent in making personal sacrifices to meet the organization's needs.

This finding affirms the study of Davies and Anderson (2010) who illustrated work ethics as a component of work engagement as one of the most critical issues in business, specifically in managing human resources. An organization's good ethical culture will provide direction and guidance for building united, harmonious, and ethical employees in various areas. There is no guidance or standard of ethics, however, that is absolute, appropriate, and applicable to any company. The ethics code is a good indicator of organizational commitment to accepting and implementing the need for ethical behaviors. Further, Work ethics can be called a cultural norm that advocates holding people accountable and fully responsible for the work they do, based on the premise that work has an intrinsic value to the individual.

Finally, the Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management (PRIME-HRM) integrates and enhances the Personnel Management Assessment and Assistance Program (PMAAP) and the CSC Agency Accreditation Program (CSCAAP). This program mandated the necessity to further enhance the ethical and professional standards among employees of the government.

Table 10. Level of Competence of Non-Teaching Personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan in Terms of Result Focus

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Achieve results with optimal use of time and resources most of the time.	3.52	Highly Competent
2. Avoid rework, mistakes, and wastage through effective work methods by placing organizational needs before personal needs.	3.44	Highly Competent
3. Deliver error-free outputs most of the time by conforming to standard operating procedures correctly and consistently. Able to produce very satisfactory quality of work in terms of usefulness/acceptability and completeness with no supervision required.	3.29	Highly Competent
4. Express a desire to do better and may express frustration at waste or inefficiency. May focus on new or more precise ways of meeting goals set.	3.44	Highly Competent
5. Make specific changes in the system or in own work methods to improve performance. Examples may include doing something better, faster, at a lower cost, more efficiently; or improving quality, customer satisfaction, morale, without setting any specific goal.	3.44	Highly Competent
Average Weighted Mean	3.43	Highly Competent

Table 10 reflects the level of competence of the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan in terms of Result Focus.

It is reflected that respondents are highly competent in delivering services because of their result-oriented features and characteristics, with a weighted mean of 3.43. In this indicator, Item 2 had the highest weighted mean of 3.52. This signifies that respondents are highly competent in achieving results with optimal use of time and resources most of the time. Meanwhile, a weighted mean of 3.29 qualifies the respondents as highly competent in delivering error-free outputs most of the time by conforming to standard operating procedures correctly and consistently. In addition, they are also able to produce a very satisfactory quality of work in terms of usefulness/acceptability and completeness with no supervision required.

Result Focus, as provided in the Individual/Office Performance Commitment Review Form and the Strategic Performance Management System, result focus implies a target and the means to accomplish the goals and target of the employee or office. In the study of Alaswad (2021), this finding is affirmed when he found out that employees are highly competent and productive when an organization sets goals and directions that are outcomes-based and result-oriented. He further stated that employees' productivity and result-oriented are critical to raising employees' performance which contributes to the

success of organizations, and it is influenced by many factors. This research aims at examining the influence of work environment, leadership styles, and organizational culture on employees' productivity. Finally, he recommended that an employee's performance depends on various factors, but the most important factor is training, which enhances the capabilities of employees.

Table 11. Level of Competence of Non-Teaching Personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan in Terms of Teamwork

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Willingly does his/her share of responsibility.	3.83	Highly Competent
2. Promote collaboration and removes barriers to teamwork and goal accomplishment across the organization.	3.66	Highly Competent
3. Apply negotiation principles in arriving at win-win agreements.	3.60	Highly Competent
4. Drive consensus and team ownership of decisions.	3.58	Highly Competent
5. Work constructively and collaboratively with others and across organizations to accomplish organizational goals and objectives.	3.66	Highly Competent
Average Weighted Mean	3.67	Highly Competent

Table 11 represents the level of competence of the respondents in terms of Teamwork.

It is reflected from the table that the personnel are highly competent in working and collaborating as a team on their workstations. An average weighted mean of 3.67 implies that working in a group is one of the top features of the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan.

Moreover, Item 1 gained the highest weighted mean of 3.83 which indicates that respondents are highly competent and are willing to do their share of responsibility. A weighted mean of 3.60 also manifests that respondents are highly competent in applying negotiation principles in arriving at win-win agreements.

Teamwork is a highly anticipated and managed organizational feature that every organizational institution hones to cultivate and gauge to effectuate and deliver public service. As pointed out by Hanaysha (2016), he examined the effects of employee empowerment, teamwork, and employee training on organizational commitment. It was found that the three variables mentioned have a significant positive impact on organizational commitment. On the other hand, Hulpia, Devos, & Keer (2011) also examined the relationship between school leadership and non-teachers organizational commitment because of the organizational culture of teamwork and collaboration. The work productivity of an individual is an organizational asset that can be equated to

progress and success. It provides satisfaction to the employees, the organization, and other stakeholders. Work productivity is also important in terms of providing sound and quality service to different stakeholders. This boiled down to the organizational virtue of working in a team.

Table 12. Level of Competence of the Non-Teaching Personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan in Terms of Service Orientation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Can explain and articulate organizational directions, issues, and problems.	3.38	Highly Competent
2. Take personal responsibility for dealing with and/or correcting customer service issues and concerns.	3.44	Highly Competent
3. Initiate activities that promote advocacy for men's and women's empowerment.	3.36	Highly Competent
4. Participate in updating office vision, mission, mandates, and strategies based on DepEd strategies and directions.	3.35	Highly Competent
5. Develop and adopt service improvement programs through simplified procedures that will further enhance service delivery.	3.44	Highly Competent
Average Weighted Mean	3.39	Highly Competent

Table 12 reflects the level of competence of the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan in terms of Service Orientation.

The data reveals that the respondents are highly competent in delivering public and general services with an average weighted mean of 3.39. Service-oriented employees exhibit high quality and standard work productivity that match their efforts, dedication, and commitment to fulfill and dispose of organizational goals and directions. As affirmed by Al-Mzary (2015), while employee performance is one of the crucial measures emphasized by top management, employees are more concerned about their service delivery and own productivity and are increasingly aware of the accelerated obsolescence of knowledge and skills in their turbulent environment. As the literature suggests, by effectively training and developing employees, they will become more aligned for career growth—career potential enhances personal motivation.

In this indicator, Item 5 had the highest weighted mean of 3.44 which indicates that respondents are highly competent in developing and adopting service improvement programs through simplified procedures that will further enhance service delivery. Moreover, Item 4 also states that respondents participate in updating of office vision, mission, mandates, and strategies based on DepEd strategies and directions.

Amisano (2010) claims that employees' service delivery is one of the most essential resources and an important asset in any organization. Various human resource functions give an organization a competitive edge, but most scholars argue that human

resource functions become only operational when training has run through them all. This makes training and development an essential feature in the survival of any organization. These are further developed by training courses. According to Barreto (2020), staff training and development have been identified by various scholars to be very crucial to an organization and its effectiveness. In light of the above, organizations are therefore encouraged to train and develop their staff to the maximum of their ability to enhance their effectiveness. Employee training and development are typically associated with the improvement of the performance, knowledge, and skills of employees in their present job position.

Table 13. Level of Competence of the Non-Teaching Employees in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan in Terms of Innovation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Examine the root cause of problems and suggest effective solutions. Fosters new ideas, processes, and suggests better ways to do things (cost and/or operational efficiency).	3.32	Highly Competent
2. Demonstrate an ability to think “beyond the box”. Continuously focuses on improving personal productivity to create higher value and results.	3.38	Highly Competent
3. Promote a creative climate and inspires co – workers to develop original ideas or solutions.	3.38	Highly Competent
4. Translate creative thinking into tangible changes and solutions that improve the work unit and organization.	3.34	Highly Competent
5. Use ingenious methods to accomplish responsibilities. Demonstrates resourcefulness and the ability to succeed with minimal resources.	3.34	Highly Competent
Average Weighted Mean	3.35	Highly Competent

The table reveals the level of competence of the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan in terms of Innovation.

It is revealed from the table that the respondents are highly competent with an average weighted mean of 3.34 in the field of Innovation as an aspect of their competence. In this indicator, it is also revealed that respondents are highly competent in demonstrating an ability to think “beyond the box” and continuously focus on improving personal productivity to create higher value and results. In addition, they are also active in promoting a creative climate and inspiring co-workers to develop original ideas or solutions. Lastly, with a weighted mean of 3.32, respondents are beyond competent in examining the root cause of problems and suggesting effective solutions. They also foster

new ideas, and processes, and suggest better ways to do things (cost and/or operational efficiency).

As affirmed by Rebore (2019), the competencies of non-teaching employees are composed of a wide array of fields that transpire from their personal and professional growth and development. These skills are anchored from the necessary competencies prescribed by their institutional organizations, job descriptions, and other organizational factors that significantly affect their upskilling processes. In this field, innovation is a factor in upgrading the level of competence of non-teaching employees in an educational institution. In the study of Wanjiku (2021), effective staff development through innovation is essential to support new approaches to gauge organizational directions, to meet changing needs of institutions. Innovation serves institutional needs and enhances the ability of the organization to meet its goals. It is an effort to help employees learn how to do their jobs better. It is important to establish working conditions to attract good-quality personnel committed to achieving organizational objectives in both the public and private sectors.

According to Khawaja & Nadeem (2013), innovation is viewed as a systematic approach to learning and development that improves individual, group, and organization. Thus, it is the series of activities organizations embark on that leads to knowledge or skills acquisition for growing purposes. Thereby, contributing to the well-being and performance of human capital, organizations, as well as society at large. Innovation serves as an act of intervention to improve an organization’s goods and services quality in stiff competition through improvements in the technical skills of employees.

Table 14. Overall Level of Competence of the Non-Teaching Personnel in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
a. Self-Management	3.55	Highly Competent
b. Professionalism and Ethics	3.61	Highly Competent
c. Result Focus	3.43	Highly Competent
d. Teamwork	3.67	Highly Competent
e. Service Orientation	3.39	Highly Competent
f. Innovation	3.35	Highly Competent
Average Weighted Mean	3.50	Highly Competent

Table 14 summarizes the level of competence of non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan from all the indicators of competence of non-teaching personnel. Overall, 104 non-teaching employees of the Schools Division Office are highly competent with an average weighted mean of 3.50. This means that they demonstrate a favorable level of competence and productivity which could result in the desired organizational outcomes. In summary, all indicators obtained a “Highly Competent” mark from the scale of level of competence Self-management has a weighted mean of 3.55; 3.61 for Professionalism and Ethics; Result Focus – has 3.43; 3.67 for Teamwork, Service Orientation has 3.39; and Innovation with 3.35.

Generally, the level of competence and the competencies present among non-teaching employees of an educational institution affect organizational productivity as a requisite in the disposition of public needs and delivery of services. These skills are anchored from the necessary competencies prescribed by their institutional organizations, job descriptions, and other organizational factors that significantly affect their upskilling processes. Emphasizing the importance of staff development in increasing effectiveness in the Schools Division, it is proven that staff development facilitates professional development for individuals and groups, enabling them to achieve their potential and contribute to the provision of excellence in the delivery of public services.

Hence, as pointed out by Dessler (2011), there is a need for an effective and trailblazing upskilling or training development program that would enhance and further develop the competence and competencies of non-teaching personnel to achieve the desired organizational goals and directions.

Comparison Between the Level of Competence of the Respondents According to the Profile Variables

Table 15. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Competence of the Respondents in terms of Self-Management when grouped According to their Profile

Variables	Probability of F	Remarks
Self-Management and Sex	0.0321	Significant
Self-Management and Age	0.0230	Significant
Self-Management and Position/Designation	0.0221	Significant
Self-Management and Type of School/Office Assignment	0.0146	Significant
Self-Management and Highest Educational Attainment	0.0294	Significant
Self-Management and Relevant Trainings Attended for Last Three Years	0.0482	Significant

Table 15 presents the results of the test of significant differences in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of self-management when grouped according to their profile.

The results show that the F-probability values are less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of self-management when grouped according to their profile. It implies that the non-teaching personnel in the City Division of Ilagan differ in their competency level in terms of self-management when clustered by their sex, age, position, type of school/office assignment, highest educational attainment, and relevant trainings attended for the last three years. Further, in comparing self-management and profile variables, the following obtained highest weighted mean for each profile variable: 3.56 for female respondents, 3.60 for respondents with age ranges from 26 to 30 years old, 4.00 for Administrative Officer I and Accountant I respondents, 3.63 for schools that are categorized as large schools, 3.80 for respondents with Doctor's

Degree, and 4.00 for relevant trainings in the fields of Human Resources and Personnel Management, Property and Resources Custodianship, and Technical Support.

This result affirmed the study of Franks (2017), it is established that self-management as an essential indicator of the level of competence of non-teaching personnel is zealous towards organizational and institutional development. In addition, when compared to the personal attributes of these non-teaching personnel, it is revealed that positive significance is present such as sex, age, position, and educational background of the respondents. Non-teaching personnel are integral to student success and educational development. Some non-teaching personnel help the schools' direction through administration and capability building towards an effective public institution and organization towards dispensing of public duties.

Further, as affirmed by Goot (2017), there is the importance of how non-teaching personnel influence an agency's overall development. In addition to serving as development navigators and helping the trajectory of most educational organizations, non-teaching personnel maintain campus operations so students can focus on learning, and teachers can focus on teaching. Thus, their engagement, professional development, and personal growth are instrumental to the functioning of higher education. Self-management is affected by employee's profile including sex and age. Franks (2017) further agreed that these variables are contributory aspects and factors in employees' manner of handling themselves in terms of relevant duties and responsibilities. Women employees, as further noted, can become strategic and organizational too as men also possess leadership and managerial abilities. Their age also manifests experiential activities that brought them to manage and handle positions or other administrative designations relative to their job description. Empirical research has instead highlighted the advantages for organizations of enhancing (for instance, by training activities) factors such as self-efficacy and the perception of control, rather than trying to remove obstacles to change according to de Jong et al. (2016). However, research that treats training for preparing an organizational change as a positive approach and emphasizes the strengths of individuals is still insufficient, and needs more empirical evidence, as advocated by recent literature.

During a radical organizational change, the perception of control and sense of self-efficacy are strategic assets for the involved people concurred by Avey et al.(2018) Successfully coping with change can be perceived by recipients as a challenging task, and can affect career choices (e.g., withdrawal behaviors or even the intention to resign). It has been found that an individual's self-efficacy plays a major role in how goals, tasks, and challenges are approached. Literature highlights that people with a strong sense of self-efficacy develop a deeper interest in the activities in which they participate, form a stronger sense of commitment to their interests and activities, recover quickly from setbacks and disappointments, and view challenging problems as tasks to be mastered. Change self-efficacy (often referred to as change confidence [CC]) is thus considered a pivotal factor in facing an organizational change successfully.

Training and educational backgrounds also affected employees' self-management mechanisms in dealing with administrative tasks. Initially, professional development aimed to improve employee performance deficiencies as emphasized by Rebore (2019). However, professional development has become a significant factor in connecting employees to their workplace and promoting group cohesiveness and a sense of community. Employees' high levels of employee engagement, training, and professional development are connected and correlate with organizational social capital.

Hence, there is a need to navigate through the competencies of non-teaching personnel by providing an upskilling program to explore and catapult the road for educational development as drivers of leadership, administration, and internal and external processes. In this study, the disparity of results between the younger and experienced employees is evidenced by the significant difference between self-management and profile variables of the age group. To resolve this, peer mentoring and coaching programs may be conducted to cater to and address the working experience gaps between the identified age groups.

Table 16. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Competence of the Respondents in Terms of Professionalism and Ethics when Grouped According to their Profile

Variables	Probability of F	Remarks
Professionalism and Ethics and Sex	0.0178	Significant
Professionalism and Ethics and Age	0.0207	Significant
Professionalism and Ethics and Position/Designation	0.0398	Significant
Professionalism and Ethics and Type of School/Office Assignment	0.0222	Significant
Professionalism and Ethics and Highest Educational Attainment	0.0300	Significant
Professionalism and Ethics and Relevant Trainings Attended for the Last Three Years	0.0446	Significant

The table shows the results of the test of significant differences in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of professionalism and ethics when grouped according to their profile.

It is evident from the results that the probability of values of F is less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of professionalism and ethics when grouped according to their profile. It states that the non-teaching varies in their competence level on professionalism and ethics when they are grouped by their different profile variables. As appended, the non-teaching personnel are fully competent in professionalism and ethics but the highest mean among them are the male, age 20-25, administrative officer 1, accountants I and II, district school, and doctoral degree. While on the training attended, out of 41 classifications, six of these are competent while the rest are fully competent in this area of competence. Further, in comparing professionalism and ethics with their profile variables, the following variables

obtained the highest weighted mean, 3.64 for male respondents, 3.93 for respondents who are from the age range of 20 to 25 years old, 4.00 for Administrative Officer I, Accountant I, and Accountant III employees, 3.73 for respondents deployed in the Schools Division Office, 3.80 for respondents who have Doctors Degree, and 4.00 for relevant trainings in the fields of Human Resources and Personnel Management, Accounting and Auditing Services, and Property Resources and Custodianship.

As established by Cuizon (2018), professionalism and ethical or work values of non-teaching personnel of an educational institution are also affected by their profile variables including personal attributes and professional circumstances. According to Judge and Bretz, as cited by Cuizon (2018), work values were found to exhibit significant effects on job choice decisions. Further, individuals were more likely to choose jobs whose value content is like their own value orientation. Donald Super recognized that the self-concept changes and develops throughout people’s lives because of experience. People successively refine their self-concept(s) over time and application to the world of work creates adaptation in their career choice. Professionalism and ethical standards are also exhibited from the respondents’ educational backgrounds and positions and designations, it is concluded that when these employees hold higher designations which are administrative, there is more likely a higher expectation of transmission and practice of moral and legal ascendancy according to their job description. All of these are further developed by training and development.

Training and development, according to Oluwaseum (2018), is an important activity that increases the performance of employees in an organization and is a building block that enhances the growth and success of an organization. Training and development are the processes of investing in people so that they are equipped to perform well and are part of an overall human resource management approach that hopefully will result in people being motivated to perform. Finally, this is a platform for them to reintroduce the ethical standards and professional activities set forth by the appropriate authorities.

Table 17. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Competence of the Respondents in Terms of Result Focus when Grouped According to their Profile

Variables	Probability of F	Remarks
Result Focus and Sex	0.0340	Significant
Result Focus and Age	0.0489	Significant
Result Focus and Position/Designation	0.0163	Significant
Result Focus and Type of School/Office Assignment	0.0478	Significant
Result Focus and Highest Educational Attainment	0.0385	Significant
Result Focus and Relevant Trainings Attended for the Last Three Years	0.0450	Significant

Table 17 displays the results of the test of significant difference in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of Result Focus when grouped according to their profile.

The results reveal that the probability values of F are less than 0.05 for this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is a significant difference in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of Result Focus when grouped according to their profile. It shows that the non-teaching personnel differ in their competence level on result focus when they are classified by sex, age, position, type of school, and highest educational attainment.

However, when grouped by relevant trainings attended from the last three years, out of 41 groupings of trainings, 11 groupings are competent in Result Focus, and 30 classifications are fully competent in Result Focus, but with different means. Result Focus When compared with their profile variables, the following obtained the highest weighted mean: 3.43 for female respondents, 3.55 for respondents who are aged 41 years old and above, 4.00 for respondents with positions of Administrative Officer I, and Accountant I, 3.49 for large schools, 3.50 for respondents with Doctor's Degree, and 4.00 for Accounting and Auditing Service s as relevant training.

The study signifies that the profile variables of the respondents differ in terms of Result Focus as an indicator of the level of competence of non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan. Results Focus is a concern for surpassing a standard of excellence. The standard may be one's past performance (striving for improvement); an objective measure (achievement orientation); challenging goals that one has set; or even improving or surpassing what has already been done (continuous improvement). Al-Mzary (2015) noted that human resources are the main asset at modern organizations, which makes the skills mastered by employees an important factor in determining the current situation as well as the future of an organization, which are impacted by the performance of the human resources. Hence, the need for rigorous and relevant training development aligned with their fields of specialization which are salient factors of a Result-Focus organization such as the Department of Education, specifically the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan.

As emphasized by Wanjiku (2021), effective staff development toward result achievement is essential to support new approaches to learning and teaching, to meet the changing needs of institutions. The result serves institutional needs and enhances the ability of the organization to meet its goals. It is an effort to help employees learn how to do their jobs better. Results may or may not include career development. It is important to establish working conditions that will attract good-quality personnel committed to the achievement of organizational objectives in both the public and private sectors. Also, there is a need to ensure the safety of employees and provide satisfactory welfare services. In the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, all cited profile variables are significantly connected to the Result Focus indicator of the level of competence which signifies that these are contributory factors in the level of competence of the respondents as administrative employees in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan.

As an implication of the results, according to Navaneetha and Bhaskar (2018), the organization and workplace need to adapt mechanisms in enhancing and providing

relative upskilling and training engagements to their employees relative to their educational developmental activities, positions or designations, and personal attributes. Thus, for organizations to achieve optimum returns from their investment, there is an imperative need to effectively manage training and development programs.

Table 18. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Competence of the Respondents in terms of Teamwork when grouped According to their Profile

Variables	Probability of F	Remarks
Teamwork and Sex	0.0207	Significant
Teamwork and Age	0.0255	Significant
Teamwork and Position/Designation	0.0481	Significant
Teamwork and Type of School/Office Assignment	0.0229	Significant
Teamwork and Highest Educational Attainment	0.0094	Significant
Teamwork and Relevant Trainings Attended for Last Three Years	0.0500	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of teamwork, when grouped according to their profile, are displayed in Table 18.

It is reflected from the results that the F-probability values are less than or equal to 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 significance level. Thus, there is a significant difference in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of teamwork when grouped according to their profile. It shows that the non-teaching personnel have varied competency in teamwork in terms of their mean when grouped by sex, age, position, type of school, and highest educational attainment. As appended, the non-teaching personnel are fully competent in teamwork but with different means. The ones that obtain the highest mean are the male, aged 20-25, Administrative Assistant I, Accountants I and III, all the Administrative Officers except Administrative Officer II, Medium School, and Doctoral Degree. On the other hand, when grouped by training attended for the last three years, out of 41 groupings four groupings are competent in teamwork, and the other 37 groupings are fully competent as indicated by their means.

It has been further revealed that teamwork and the highest educational attainment are highly significant. This implies that teamwork is highly significant when compared to their highest educational attainment which indicates the level of educational attainment of the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division Office of the City. Teamwork and highest educational attainment are two comparative and relative variables that indicate that when educational attainment is high, then there is a probability that such an employee is manifesting the thrusts and features of a contributing member in an organization which is an aspect of teamwork.

The result affirms that individuals vary in terms of their level of competence in teamwork. As agreed by Nda & Fard (2013), teamwork is the backbone of effective

communication within a company. When employees work as individuals or independently on projects, they may not readily share knowledge or new information. This lack of communication increases the time it takes to complete projects, tasks, or the development of solutions. Teamwork promotes conversation between employees regarding the task at hand, possibly preventing employees from working in opposite directions. Therefore, training and development must be designed and delivered to meet the needs of all employees in such a way that the employees will not only be productive but also be satisfied. Training and development have a positive impact on the employees to carry out their work more effectively, increasing their interpersonal and technical abilities, teamwork, job confidence, and work motivation.

Consequently, when teams, groups, or individual employees possess varied levels of teamwork, there is a variety of mechanisms for dealing with clients, administrative tasks, and other aspects of public services. This is better achieved through upskilling programs. As emphasized by Hamid (2021), upskilling is a way of enhancing employee commitment and maximizing employee potential. Training is an instrument that fundamentally affects the successful accomplishment of organizations' goals and objectives. Further, it is well known that teamwork develops thanks to a social learning process. Indeed, the growth of self-efficacy continues to evolve throughout people's working lives as they acquire new skills, experience, and understanding. Training processes should therefore play a strategic role in addressing and developing teamwork in preparation for an organizational change.

Table 19. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Competence of the Respondents in terms of Service Orientation when Grouped According to their Profile

Variables	Probability of F	Remarks
Service Orientation and Sex	0.0472	Significant
Service Orientation and Age	0.0229	Significant
Service Orientation and Position/Designation	0.0051	Significant
Service Orientation and Type of School/Office Assignment	0.0071	Significant
Service Orientation and Highest Educational Attainment	0.1233	Not Significant
Service Orientation and Relevant Trainings Attended for Last Three Years	0.0400	Significant

Table 19 discloses the results of the test of significant differences in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of service orientation when grouped according to their profile.

The results show that the F-probability values are less than 0.05 except for the highest educational attainment. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of service orientation when grouped according to their sex, age, position, type of school/office assignment, and relevant trainings attended for the last three years. It states that the non-teaching personnel differ in their competency level

on service orientation in terms of their means when they are grouped by the aforesaid profiles. As evidenced by the mean, the non-teaching personnel are fully competent in service orientation when classified by sex, age, and type of school but with different means. The highest means are obtained by males, ages 20-25, and medium school.

Regarding position, out of 10 positions, one is competent, that is the Administrative Assistant, and the other nine designations are fully competent in this area but with varied means. On the other hand, with regards to training attended for the last three years, out of 41 groupings, 24 are fully competent and 17 are competent in service orientation but with varied means. Service Orientation, when compared to their profile variables, 3.47 for male respondents, 3.67 for respondents who are aged from 20 to 25 years old, 4.00 for respondents with positions Administrative Officer I, Accountant I, and Accountant III, 3.50 for medium schools, 3.43 for college graduates, and 4.00 for Human Resources and Personnel Management as relevant training.

However, there is no significant difference in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of service orientation when they are grouped according to highest educational attainment. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. It implies that the non-teaching personnel do not differ in their competence level on service orientation when they are classified by the said profile. It states further that the respondents have similarities in their competence level on service orientation regardless of their highest educational attainment. Nonetheless, it has been further revealed that service orientation and highest educational attainment of the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan are not significant when compared together.

Service Orientation is an equivalent of service efficiency directed and provided to clients and organizations whom the agency or institution they serve. The impact of service orientation on employees' performance and competence has been a leading factor in the development of organizational institutions, specifically those who are in public service. Hence, as discussed by Tahir et al. (2014), service orientation is affected by the position or designation and the work assignment or station of administrative employees. Some indicators of service orientation are measured in various parameters such as participation, transparency, environment, and provision of general administrative and technical services to ensure the general delivery of public services. These are manifested by the professional status of administrative employees as mentioned in terms of their status and standing in an organization.

Further, service orientation could also be manifested by the administrative employees' age and experience. In addition, employees' sex also differ in terms of service orientation as some studies including Hafeez & Akbar (2015), divulged that women generally provide clearer directions for organizations in terms of service orientation, while male employees are generally akin to administrative management and leadership. However, this was negated by stating that sexual differences have little to no effect in terms of the service orientation of administrative employees in an educational institution.

Finally, in terms of relevant training attended, these trainings anchored from the job descriptions, duties, and responsibilities of non-teaching personnel of an educational agency provide for clearer manifestations of their service orientation. Darcy mentions that training and development, taken together, help employees develop better skills, change their attitudes toward work, and improve their knowledge regarding their field. The main purpose of training and development is to improve employee competencies so that organizations can maximize the efficiency and effectiveness of their employees. As an effect on the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, some benefits of this program are the increase in the productivity of workers, development of skills, and greater proficiency in work. If employees are to experience effectiveness on the job, they need to acquire and develop knowledge and skills.

Furthermore, the result also shows that when compared together, the variable of service orientation is highly significant to position/designation and type of school or office assignment. In the first comparison, this means that the position or designation of a non-teaching employee could influence his or her service orientation. As established, service orientation is tantamount to service efficiency. Hence, if an employee is in a higher position or designation with greater responsibilities, service efficiency is expected. Service Orientation is an equivalent of service efficiency directed and provided to clients and organizations whom the agency or institution they serve. Moreover, service orientation could also be influenced by the type of school or office assignment. This implies that when the workplace is favorable or convenient to the employee considering significant and relevant factors, it follows that service efficiency could be raked.

Table 20. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Competence of the Respondents in terms of Innovation when Grouped According to their Profile

Variables	Probability of F	Remarks
Innovation and Sex	0.0474	Significant
Innovation and Age	0.0397	Significant
Innovation and Position/Designation	0.0146	Significant
Innovation and Type of School/Office Assignment	0.0103	Significant
Innovation and Highest Educational Attainment	0.0368	Significant
Innovation and Relevant Trainings Attended for Last Three Years	0.0500	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the level of competence of the respondents in terms of Innovation, when grouped according to their profile, are exhibited in Table 20.

It is evident from the results that the probability values of F are less than or equal to 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the competence level of the respondents in terms of innovation when grouped according to their profile. It shows that the non-teaching

personnel differ in their competence level on innovation when they are grouped by sex, age, position, type of school/office assignment, highest educational attainment, and relevant trainings attended for the last three years. As appended, the non-teaching personnel who got the highest mean are the male, aged 20-25, administrative officer I and Accountant I and III, medium school and college graduates. While, on training, out of 41 groupings, 27 are fully competent, 13 are competent, and one is competent in innovation as evidenced by the means. When compared to innovation, the following obtained the highest weighted means for every profile variable: 3.47 for male respondents, 3.73 for respondents aged from 20 to 25 years old, 4.00 for respondents who are designated as Administrative Officer I, Accountant I, and Accountant III, 3.41 for medium schools, 3.41 for college graduates, and 3.90 for Property and Resources Custodianship as relevant training.

The result affirms that the respondents differ in their level of competence in terms of Innovation when compared to their profile variables. According to Sarkodie (2011), in terms of innovation, it is the systematic and practical application of solutions, methods, and mechanisms adapted to resolve or further enhance an organization's policy, scheme, or programs. In the Department of Education, several innovations are made in instructional and curriculum development. On the other hand, innovations are also encouraged and further developed in the administrative section of the Department. Public agencies such as the Department of Education are considered the cornerstone for intelligent and responsible citizenship. To enhance its efficiency and effectiveness, it is necessary to conduct innovations for the personnel development of all its employees at all levels. These employees are assets or resources to be valued, developed, and utilized in the delivery of basic services to the interest of the public. They must have the necessary skills and knowledge to better serve the people's needs and concerns.

These factors of competence in innovation include the personal and professional dealings of the respondents as they gauge the innovative levels of these employees to better serve the stakeholders. Another factor is upskilling or training engagement which trail-blazed organizations to further enhance and improve. In the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, these are engaged to boost the skills and competencies of administrative employees including the non-teaching personnel who are deployed within the schools of the Division Office.

Further, Edralin (2011) noted that training has been at the forefront factor of developing employees from among organizations, associations, agencies, and human resources. In terms of innovation, respondents are optimistic and enthusiastic if nominated for a training and development program. Results also revealed possible enablers of employee's ability to learn. Work-related and personal commitments, as well as training programs, including delivery methods, materials, and instructors, turned favorable for respondents considering their situation signifying those employees genuinely value training.

Performance of Non-Teaching Personnel based on the Key Result Areas (KRAs)

Table 21. Performance of Administrative Officer V Employee/s Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Officer V (Admin)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Administrative Policies and Guidelines	5	Outstanding
2. Personnel Administration	5	Outstanding
3. Records Management	5	Outstanding
4. Cash Management	5	Outstanding
5. Supply and Procurement	5	Outstanding
6. Security and Custody of Properties	5	Outstanding
7. Maintenance of SDO Grounds and Facilities	4	Very Satisfactory
8. Administrative Services Performance	5	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.88	Outstanding

The table above portrays the performance of an employee who is holding the position of Administrative Officer V based on the Key Result Areas of the Office Performance Commitment Review Form. The data shows that the employee gained an overall rating of 4.88 which means that the employee excelled with an Outstanding Performance to the prescribed duties and responsibilities as Administrative Officer V. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records.

Further, the employee achieved a perfect score of 5 from each Key Result Area including Administrative Policies and Guidelines, Personnel Administration, Records Management, Cash Management, Supply and Procurement, Security and Custody of Properties, and Administrative Services Performance. However, a score of 4 was also marked in the KRA of Maintenance of SDO Grounds and Facilities. The Schools Division Office (SDO) empowers schools and Learning Centers (LC) and engages partners and communities in the delivery of quality basic education that is accessible to all.

According to the 2022 DepEd-Civil Service Commission guidelines, this administrative position aims to provide management with economical, efficient, and effective budgeting services and reliable and timely financial information for decision-making towards the cost-effective utilization of financial resources of the division. Further, this also aims to supervise the team that will provide the Schools Division Office with timely, responsive, and economical administrative services in personnel and records management, cash disbursement, procurement, security and custody of the property, and the maintenance of facilities, to ensure efficient operation of the schools division office towards enabling schools and learning centers provide accessibly and quality and basic education.

Table 22. Performance of Administrative Officer IV (Personnel) Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Officer IV (Personnel)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Recruitment, Selection and Placement	5.00	Outstanding
2. Personnel Actions	5.00	Outstanding
3. Salary Administration and Personnel Records	5.00	Outstanding
4. Benefits Administration	5.00	Outstanding
5. Personnel Information System	5.00	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	5.00	Outstanding

The table above represents the performance of the employee holding the position of Administrative Officer IV in the field of Personnel Management based on the Key Result Areas of the Office Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records.

It is revealed that the employee achieved an Outstanding Performance with a rating of 5 as the overall rating. These Key Result Areas include Recruitment, Selection and Placement, Personnel Actions, Salary Administration and Personnel Records, Benefits Administration, and Personnel Information System.

As provided by the DepEd-CSC in 2022, this administrative position aims to provide personnel administration services to the management and personnel of the Schools Division in the areas of recruitment and selection, personnel administration, compensation and benefits administration, personnel records, while ensuring adherence to the standards, rules, and regulations in personnel administration of government oversight agencies (CSC, DBM, COA, etc.).

Table 23. Performance of Administrative Officer IV (Records) Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Officer IV (Record Officer II)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Records Management System	5.00	Outstanding
2. Receiving and Releasing	5.00	Outstanding
3. Documentation Authentication and Verification	5.00	Outstanding
4. Reporting	4.90	Outstanding
5. Technical Assistance	5.00	Outstanding
6. Unit Performance	4.88	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.96	Outstanding

Table 23 reflects the overall performance of an employee holding the position of Administrative Officer IV in the field of Records Management based on the Key Result Areas of the Office Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their individual files or records.

The data highlights that the employees maintained an Outstanding Performance with an overall rating of 4.96. It is further divulged that the said employee garnered perfect

ratings in the Key Result Areas of the Records Management System, Receiving and Releasing, Documentation Authentication and Verification, and Technical Assistance. The Key Result Areas of Reporting and Unit Performance obtained a rating of 4.90 and 4.88, respectively.

Accordingly, this position, as per DepEd-CSC is characterized by the aim to establish and maintain a records management system, including the creation, classification, storage, maintenance, use, and disposition of operating records and documents of permanent, legal, and historical value and ensure the security, preservation, and efficient access and retrieval of such records when needed by the school's division office management and staff.

Table 24. Performance of Administrative Officer IV (Cash) Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Officer IV (Cash)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Cash Collection	5.00	Outstanding
2. Cash Disbursement Payment & Remittance	5.00	Outstanding
3. Liquidation and Reporting	5.00	Outstanding
4. Secondary Duties	4.90	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.98	Outstanding

Table 24 manifests the overall performance of the Administrative Officer IV employee for Cash Management based on the Key Result Areas of the Office Performance Commitment and Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records.

An overall rating of 4.98 shows that the said employee is qualified to have an Outstanding Performance. For each Key Result Area, a score of 5 dominated the areas of Cash Collection, Cash Disbursement Payment and Remittance, and Liquidation and Reporting, while Secondary Duties had a score of 4.90.

As per DepEd-CSC is characterized by the aim to manage cash collections, disbursements, liquidations, and preparation of reports to the accounting office to ensure proper utilization and timely disbursement of funds and liquidation of cash advances to pay for government obligations in accordance with accounting and auditing rules and regulations.

Table 25. Performance of Administrative Officer IV (Supply Officer II/Property) Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Officer IV (Supply Officer II/Property)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Policies, Standards, Guidelines, Systems	4.70	Outstanding
2. Property and Acquisition	4.13	Very Satisfactory

3. Delivery Inspection and Acceptance	4.50	Outstanding
4. Custodianship	4.83	Outstanding
5. Disposal	4.35	Very Satisfactory
OVERALL RATING	4.50	Outstanding

Table 25 shows the performance of an employee with the position of Administrative Officer IV as the Supply and Property Officer of the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan.

From the data presented, the said employee had an overall rating of 4.50 which means that an Outstanding Performance was manifested from the Office Performance Commitment Review Form. The Key Result Area of Policies, Standards, Guidelines, and Systems had an outstanding rating of 4.70, Property and Acquisition had a Very Satisfactory rating of 4.13, Delivery Inspection and Acceptance had an Outstanding Performance of 4.50, Custodianship obtained an Outstanding Rating of 4.83, and Disposal as the last Key Result Area had a Very Satisfactory rating of 4.35. These Very Satisfactory remarks are implications of the insufficient relevant trainings of the said employees in the fields of Disposal and Property Acquisition as essential Key Result Areas of their designation or position.

In place of this, the upskilling program in the fields of result focus and innovation signifies the necessity to include this position in the development and evaluation of training development for improved and better performance in the Individual Performance Review Commitment Form. During the interview, respondents under this position/designation narrated that they obtained a Very Satisfactory rating in the fields of Property and Acquisition, and Disposal due to the complexity and difficulty of the nature of these Key Result Areas as Supply/Property Officer. Due to the demands and necessities in purchases, procurement, and inventories, respondents had simple inconsistencies with data and supply management. Nonetheless, they still managed to obtain an above-average rating for the identified Key Result Areas of their IPCRF/OPCRF.

Table 26. Performance of Administrative Officer II Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Officer II	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Personnel Administration	4.76	Outstanding
2. Property Custodianship	4.71	Outstanding
3. General Administrative Support	4.78	Outstanding
4. Financial Management	4.76	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.75	Outstanding

Table 26 presents the performance of non-teaching personnel who hold the position of Administrative Officer II based on their Key Result Areas of the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated upon checking their files or records.

Based on the presented data above, non-teaching personnel who are designated in the schools of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan had an overall rating of 4.75 which signifies that they had an Outstanding Performance as prescribed from their administrative position. These employees possessed and performed well in the duties and responsibilities as Administrative Officers of elementary schools, integrated schools, and secondary schools in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan. Moreover, for each Key Result Area, employees obtained an Outstanding Performance for each Key Result Area including Personnel Administration, Property Custodianship, General Administrative Support, and Financial Management.

According to DepEd-CSC, Administrative Officer IV (Supply/Property) is guided to provide technical services to the management and staff of the SDO in relation to procurement (using alternative mode), inspection, acceptance, issuance, storage, maintenance, and inventory of material resources, equipment, and properties to support the efficient operations of the schools' division office in managing the delivery of quality basic education and, facilitate the disposal of waste materials and unserviceable equipment to derive economic benefit and maintain orderliness and efficient use of office space.

Table 27. Performance of Administrative Officer II (Personnel) Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Officer II (Personnel/HRMO I)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Salary Administration and Personnel Records	5.00	Outstanding
2. Benefits Administration	5.00	Outstanding
3. Personnel Information System	5.00	Outstanding
4. Other Duties	4.90	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.98	Outstanding

The table above reveals the performance of Administrative Officer II employees designated for Personnel Management in the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their individual files or records.

The data established those employees under this KRA for Administrative Officer II (Personnel/Human Resource Management Officer) achieved an overall rating of 4.98 which means that they showcased an Outstanding Performance from the last calendar year. These employees had a perfect score of 5 in the Key Result Areas of Salary Administration and Personnel Records, Benefits Administration, and Personnel Information System. Their Other Duties also had an Outstanding rating of 4.90.

As provided under DepEd-CSC, this is administrative work in coordinating and assisting a higher-level administrator with the management of an agency. An employee in this class is responsible for performing administrative staff assignments and office management work for a division or organizational unit. Work differs from that of

Administrative Officer I by the complexity of assignments and independent decision-making, but an employee is allowed to use his judgment where necessary. General supervision is received from a higher-level officer through conferences and review of work for compliance with departmental rules and regulations. Supervision is exercised over a small clerical staff.

Table 28. Performance of Administrative Officer I (IUs) Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Officer I (IUs)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Personnel Administration	5.00	Outstanding
2. Property Custodianship	5.00	Outstanding
3. General Administrative Support	4.90	Outstanding
4. Financial Management	4.90	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.95	Outstanding

This table provides the result of the performance survey of Administrative Officer I employees in the Implementing Units Office based on their Key Result Areas of the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their individual files or records.

In this administrative position, non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan had an Outstanding Performance of 4.95 as their overall rating. On the other hand, they had a respective final score of 5 for the Key Result Areas of Personnel Administration and Property Custodianship. A rating of 4.90 was respectively achieved in the Key Result Areas of General Administrative Support and Financial Management. According to DepEd-CSC, this position supervises and assists in the direction of a major department; assists a senior official in the development of operating procedures; confers with him on matters affecting personnel, policy and other administrative problems; makes complex operational decisions; supervises a number of subordinate staff.

Table 29. Performance of Administrative Assistant III Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Assistant III	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Office Schedules	4.63	Outstanding
2. Communications/Documents	4.68	Outstanding
3. Guests Reception	4.70	Outstanding
4. Records/Files	4.83	Outstanding
5. Personnel Matters	4.75	Outstanding
6. Technical/Administrative	4.65	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.70	Outstanding

Table 29 shows the performance of Administrative Assistant III employees of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan based on their Key Result Areas of the Individual Performance Commitment Form. Based on the data presented, these employees had an

overall rating of 4.70 which implies that they had an Overall Outstanding Performance as Administrative Assistant III employees as prescribed by their duties and responsibilities. Outstanding ratings were also manifested in all Key Result Areas including Office Schedules, Communications/Documents, Guests Reception, Records/Files, Personnel Matters, and Technical or Administrative Support. In an interview, performance ratings were validated upon checking their files or records.

As emphasized by DepEd-CSC, this position seeks to provide prompt and quality support service to the SDS by implementing administrative systems, and procedures, and monitoring administrative projects for the SDS to perform his/her duties efficiently.

Table 30. Performance of Administrative Assistant III Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Assistant III (IUs)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Accounting Services	4.63	Outstanding
2. Salary Administration and Payroll Processing	4.63	Outstanding
3. Payroll-related Services	4.72	Outstanding
4. Budgeting Services	4.69	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.67	Outstanding

The preceding table showcases the performance evaluation results of Administrative Assistant III employees of the Implementing Unit Offices of the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records.

It is revealed that employees were outstanding in all the Key Result Areas including Accounting Services, Salary Administration and Payroll Processing, Payroll-Related Services, and Budgeting Services. Overall, they had an outstanding performance with an overall rating of 4.67.

Further, DepEd-CSC detailed that this position shall provide assistance on the finance-related functions in schools and facilitate efficiency in SDO and school operations such as accounting, budgeting, cash management, and payroll services, to ensure efficient office operations.

Table 31. Performance of Administrative Assistant III (Non-IUs) Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Assistant III (Non-IUs)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Financial Records and Reports	4.69	Outstanding
2. Account Tracking	4.70	Outstanding
3. Financial Transactions Recording Procedures	4.64	Outstanding
4. Human Resource Management	4.38	Very Satisfactory
OVERALL RATING	4.60	Outstanding

The preceding table illustrates the performance of the Administrative Assistant III employees as Non-Implementing Unit employees of the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records.

It is divulged that employees under this administrative position perform well with an overall rating of 4.60 which implies that they had an Outstanding Performance. In addition, these employees had an Outstanding performance in the Key Result Areas of Financial Records and Reports, Account Tracking, and Financial Transactions Recording Procedures. In the Key Result Area of Human Resource Management, they had a rating of 4.38 which means that they obtained a Very Satisfactory remark. This Very Satisfactory remark implies that there is a necessity to upgrade the field or area of the KRA to align objectives based on the necessary skills to be obtained and possessed by the employee.

In the development of an upskilling program, employees in this position are recommended to undergo further training and a series of upskilling programs to transform their overall individual performance specifically in the fields of self-management and result focus. During the interview, the respondents detailed the recurring causes and issues that arose during the year of service because of some issues and concerns that arose from their designation. In the position of Administrative Officer III (Non-Implementing Units), they had issues with Human Resource Management due to the scattered deployment of employees under their designation and assigned workplaces. It is also cited that the far-flung distances of schools led to difficulty in the daily assistance of technical aid and administrative services. However, this did not hinder them to still obtain a rating of Very Satisfactory.

Moreover, employees in this position, according to DepEd-CSC, aim to maintain and safeguard the books, records, and supporting schedules of the Division Office by keeping track of accounts and verifying the accuracy of procedures used for recording financial data that are necessary for the preparation of timely and reliable reports which will aid the management in making informed decisions.

Table 32. Performance of Administrative Assistant III Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Assistant III (Senior Bookkeeper)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Financial Records and Reports	4.82	Outstanding
2. Account Tracking	4.85	Outstanding
3. Financial Transactions Recording Procedure	4.84	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.84	Outstanding

The table presented above shows the performance of Administrative Assistant III Employees as Senior Bookkeepers of the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records.

As presented, employees holding this administrative position received an overall rating of 4.84 which means that they had an Outstanding Performance as non-teaching personnel. Specifically, they also had outstanding remarks in the Key Result Areas of Financial Records and Reports, Account Tracking, and Financial Transactions Recording Procedure.

As noted under DepEd-CSC, this position seeks to maintain and safeguard the books, records, and supporting schedules of the Division Office by keeping track of accounts and verifying the accuracy of procedures used for recording financial data that are necessary for the preparation of timely and reliable reports which will aid the management in making informed decisions.

Table 33. Performance of Administrative Assistant II Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Assistant II (IUs)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Accounting Services	4.73	Outstanding
2. Budgeting Services	4.78	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.75	Outstanding

This table presents the performance of Administrative Assistant II employees of the Implementing Unit Offices of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records.

Here, respondents had an overall rating of 4.75 which signifies their outstanding performance as indicated by their description of duties and responsibilities in the fields of Accounting Services and Budgeting Services. This position, according to DepEd-CSC, shall assist in finance and administrative-related services such as accounting, budgeting, and payroll processing and ensuring efficient office operations.

Table 34. Performance of Administrative Assistant II Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Assistant II	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Accounting Records	4.66	Outstanding
2. Accounting Reports	4.74	Outstanding
3. Loan Verification	4.77	Outstanding
4. Salary Administration and Personnel Records	4.50	Outstanding
5. Finance-Related Reports and Records Management	4.53	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.64	Outstanding

The table above exhibits the performance of Administrative Assistant II employees deployed in schools within the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records.

From the data presented, it can be gleaned that Administrative Assistant II employees of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan performed Outstanding with an overall rating of 4.64 with the same qualitative description for the ratings in the Key Result Areas including Accounting Records, Accounting Reports, Loan Verification, Salary Administration and Personnel Records, and Finance-Related Reports and Records Management.

According to DepEd-CSC, this position shall assist the Senior Bookkeeper and/or School Head in the performance of their functions, such as but not limited to undertaking the necessary accounting, budgeting, cash management, payroll services, and other finance-related, to ensure efficient office operations.

Table 35. Performance of Administrative Assistant II Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Assistant II (Accounting Clerk)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Accounting Records	4.83	Outstanding
2. Accounting Reports	4.85	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.84	Outstanding

Table 35 presents the performance of Administrative Assistant II employees deployed as Accounting Clerks in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan based on their Key Result Areas of the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records.

It is shown that these employees had an Outstanding Performance from last year with an overall rating of 4.84. The same qualitative remarks were also obtained in the Key Result Areas of Accounting Records and Accounting Reports. As guided by DepEd-CSC, this position has its goal to support accounting operations by filing documents; reconciling statements; and running software programs.

Table 36. Performance of Administrative Assistant II (Non-IUs) Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Assistant II (Non-IUs)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Financial Records and Reports	4.69	Outstanding
2. Budget Preparation Execution and Reports	4.61	Outstanding
3. Human Resource Management	4.68	Outstanding
4. Other Task	4.69	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.67	Outstanding

The table preceding table divulges the overall performance of Administrative Assistant II employees deployed in the Non-Implementing Units of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records.

An overall rating of 4.67 qualified the respondents to excel with an Outstanding Performance which is also evident from their ratings in every Key Result Area including Financial Records and Reports, Budget Preparation, Execution, and Reports, Human Resource Management, and Other Tasks.

According to DepEd-CSC, Administrative Assistant II positions are characterized by Accounting, Budgeting, and administrative duties. The Accounting Services maintain financial records and reports to provide management with information for decision-making and accounting reports to oversight agencies to ensure the proper utilization of funds in accordance with accounting and auditing rules and regulations. The Budgeting Services provides management with economical, efficient, and effective budgeting services and reliable and timely financial information for decision-making toward the cost-effective allocation and utilization of financial resources of the schools division.

Table 37. Performance of Administrative Assistant I Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Assistant I (Budget Officer I)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Budget Preparation, Execution, and Accountability Data and Documents	4.93	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.93	Outstanding

Table 36 manifests the performance of Administrative Assistant I employees deployed as Budget Officers of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan based on the Key Result Area of the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their files or records.

With a single Key Result Area, the overall outstanding performance in Budget Preparation, Execution, and Accountability of Data and Documents had an overall rating of 4.93. Further, according to DepEd-CSC, this position aims to provide general and routine clerical support to the budgeting officer in the preparation of budgetary requirements needed for submission to the DBM and reports in compliance with other attached agencies, and to provide administrative support to the Finance Services functions.

Table 38. Performance of Administrative Assistant I (IUs) Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Officer I (IUs)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Personnel Administration	5.00	Outstanding
2. Property Custodianship	5.00	Outstanding
3. General Administrative Support	4.90	Outstanding
4. Financial Management	4.90	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.95	Outstanding

The table above reflects the performance of Administrative Assistant I employees deployed in the Implementing Units in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their individual files or records.

As shown above, the employees had an overall rating of 4.95 which directly translates to an Outstanding Performance. They also had an Outstanding Performance for every Key Result Area including Personnel Administration, Property Custodianship, General Administrative Support, and Financial Management. According to DepEd-CSC, this position aims to provide general and routine clerical support to the budgeting officer in the preparation of budgetary requirements needed for submission to the DBM and reports in compliance with other attached agencies, and to provide administrative support to the Finance Services functions.

Table 39. Performance of Administrative Aide VI (Data Entry Machine Operator) Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Aide VI (Data Entry Machine Operator)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Receiving and Releasing	4.50	Outstanding
2. Documents Authentication, Verification and Certification	4.40	Very Satisfactory
3. Reporting	4.30	Very Satisfactory
4. Technical Assistance	4.20	Very Satisfactory
OVERALL RATING	4.35	Very Satisfactory

Table 39 represents the overall performance of Administrative Aide VI employees deployed as Data Entry Machine Operators based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Review Commitment Form. It is categorically presented that these respondents had an Overall Performance of Very Satisfactory with an overall rating of 4.35. The same qualitative remark was obtained in the following Key Result Areas: Receiving and Releasing, Documents Authentication, Verification, and Certification, Reporting, and Technical Assistance.

Three areas obtained a Very Satisfactory remark due to insufficiency of trainings relevant to the areas or fields of reporting, receiving, and releasing, and documents authentication, verification, and certification. During the interview, employees under the position of Administrative Aide VI detailed that due to their lack of educational experience and training attendance, they somehow obtained a Very Satisfactory rating from almost all their Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. They added that apart from these cited reasons, the nature of their task is technical and purely administrative. Their inability to properly manage papers relative to their job descriptions had led to this result. On the other hand, the necessity for an upskilling program was highly recommended by their immediate heads and supervisors.

With this result, there is a necessity to augment the training and upskilling development of employees in this position. These fields to be included in their upskilling program are Result Focus, Self-Management, Innovation, and Service Orientation.

Further, DepEd-CSC expressly states that this position provides administrative support to the Records Officer in the maintenance of a records management system for the creation, classification, storage, maintenance, use, and disposition of operating records and documents of permanent, legal, and historical value and ensure the security, preservation, and efficient access and retrieval of such records when needed by the school's division office management and staff.

Table 40. Performance of Administrative Aide VI (Cash) Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Aide VI (Cash)	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Cash Collection	4.90	Outstanding
2. Cash Disbursement Payment & Remittance	4.80	Outstanding
3. Liquidation and Reporting	4.80	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.83	Outstanding

Table 40 reveals the performance of Administrative Aide VI employees deployed as Cash Disbursement Officers based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form. These employees have shown an outstanding performance as evidenced by their overall rating of 4.83, and outstanding performance in every Key Result Area of Cash Collection, Cash Disbursement Payment and Remittance, and Liquidation and Reporting. In an interview, performance ratings were validated upon checking their files or records. Moreover, this position as per DepEd-CSC, this position aims to assist the AO IV for Cash, in cash collection and disbursement, and the preparations and submission of cash-related reports.

Table 41. Performance of Administrative Aide IV Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Administrative Aide IV	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Messengerial and Photocopying	4.74	Outstanding
2. Recording	4.80	Outstanding
3. Communication	4.64	Outstanding
4. Plots/Schedules Activities	4.66	Outstanding
5. Record Management	4.68	Outstanding
6. Administrative Support	4.72	Outstanding
7. Secretariat/Frontline	4.65	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.70	Outstanding

The table above represents the overall performance of Administrative Aide IV employees based on the Key Result Areas of their Individual Performance Commitment

Review Form. In an interview, performance ratings were validated upon checking their files or records.

These respondent employees had an overall rating of 4.70 which signifies that they had an exemplary performance. They also had an outstanding performance for all the Key Result Areas including Messengerial and Photocopying, Recording, Communication, Plots/Schedules Activities, Records management, Administrative Support, and Secretariat or Frontline. In lieu of these Key Result Areas, the Department of Education – Civil Service Commission also provided guidelines on the job description of this position. As noted by DepEd-CSC, this position assists in various aspects of general administrative processes such as purchasing, facilities operations, office automation, safety, human resources, customer service, public information, and other areas. Participates in meetings and presents data to assist managers in making operations and administrative decisions.

Table 42. Performance of Budget Officer III Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Budget Officer III	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Budget Preparation	5.00	Outstanding
2. Budget Execution	5.00	Outstanding
3. Budget Accountability and Reporting	5.00	Outstanding
4. Budget Systems Maintenance, Monitoring & Evaluation	5.00	Outstanding
5. Technical Assistance	5.00	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	5.00	Outstanding

The preceding table is representation of the overall performance of Budget Officer III employees based on the Key Result Areas of their Office Performance Commitment Review Form. With an overall rating of 5.00, these non-teaching personnel had a perfect and outstanding performance from the last calendar year. They also had perfect scores for all the Key Result Areas including Budget Preparation, Budget Execution, Budget Accountability and reporting, Budget Systems Maintenance, Monitoring and Evaluation, and Technical Assistance. In an interview, performance ratings were validated upon checking their files or records.

DepEd-CSC provides that this position seeks to provide management with economical, efficient, and effective budgeting services and reliable and timely financial information for decision-making toward the cost-effective utilization of financial resources of the division.

Table 43. Performance of Accountant III Employee Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Accountant III	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Financial Records and Reports	5.00	Outstanding
2. Financial Systems Maintenance	5.00	Outstanding
3. Monitoring and Evaluation	4.87	Outstanding
4. Technical Assistance	5.00	Outstanding

5. Accounting Services Performance	5.00	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	4.97	Outstanding

Table 43 shows the performance of an Accountant III employee from the last calendar year based on the Key Result Areas of the Office Performance Commitment Review Form. An overall rating of 4.97 qualified the respondent to have an outstanding performance. In an interview, performance ratings were validated upon checking their files or records.

The employee also had a perfect score for the Key Result Areas including Financial Records and Reports, Financial Systems Maintenance, Technical Assistance, and Accounting Services Performance. Moreover, the employee had a rating of 4.87 in the Key Result Area of Monitoring and Evaluation.

DepEd-CSC provides that Accountant III develop and implement complex accounting system modifications and participate in the analysis and implementation of financial standards, policies, and procedures. Accountant III is distinguished from Accountant II in the amount and type of responsibility undertaken and direction received and exercised. DepEd Accountant III (Salary Grade 19) analyzes and attests to the accuracy of accounting records and reports and provides information and advice to the management of the schools division to ensure that the utilization of funds for basic education is maximized and compliant with government accounting rules and regulations, and ensures that financial reports will be fairly presented and that all recordable transactions must be taken up accurately in the books and that all disbursements are properly documented and following laws, rules, and regulations. Moreover, they are tasked to supervise, facilitate, and monitor the work of the accounting personnel and provide technical assistance to school heads and implementing units to ensure proper utilization of funds and preparation of reliable and timely financial reports.

Table 44. Performance of Accountant I Employees Based on the Key Result Areas

KRA for Accountant I	RATING	Qualitative Description
1. Financial Records and Reports	5.00	Outstanding
2. Financial Systems Maintenance	5.00	Outstanding
3. Monitoring and Evaluation	5.00	Outstanding
4. Technical Assistance	5.00	Outstanding
5. Accounting Services Performance	5.00	Outstanding
OVERALL RATING	5.00	Outstanding

The table above shows the overall performance of Accountant I employee based on the Key Result Areas of their Office Performance Commitment Review Form. The employee swept a perfect score for all the Key Result Areas including Financial Records and Reports, Financial Systems Maintenance, Monitoring and Evaluation, Technical Assistance, and Accounting Services Performance, and an Outstanding Performance. In

an interview, performance ratings were validated and upon checking their individual files or records.

Finally, as provided under DepEd-CSC, this position performs entry-level accounting work. Work involves maintaining, posting, and balancing accounting and financial statements, records, documents, or reports. May specialize in some phase of accounting work such as federal funds accounting, property and equipment control, cost, budgeting, or bond servicing. This position also prepares periodic Financial Statements and other related reports in accordance with accounting and auditing rules and regulations, and checks the accuracy, validity and appropriateness of income and expenditure transactions. accounting information.

Lastly, this position is also tasked to supervise, facilitate, and monitor the work of the accounting personnel and provide technical assistance to school heads and implementing units to ensure proper utilization of funds and preparation of reliable and timely financial reports.

Comparison Between the Performance of Non-Teaching Personnel based on the Key Result Areas (KRAs) and their Profile Variables

Table 45. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Performance of Non-Teaching Personnel in terms of Key Result Areas when grouped According to their Profile

Variables	Probability of F	Remarks
Performance and Sex	0.0440	Significant
Performance and Age	0.0200	Significant
Performance and Position/Designation	0.0009	Significant
Performance and Type of School/Office Assignment	0.0161	Significant
Performance and Highest Educational Attainment	0.0135	Significant
Performance and Relevant Trainings Attended for Last Three Years	0.0446	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the performance of the non-teaching personnel in terms of the Key Result Area when grouped according to their profile are disclosed in Table 45.

It is revealed from the results that the f-probability values are less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the performance of non-teaching personnel in terms of their KRA when grouped according to their profile. It states that the non-teaching personnel differ in their performance when they clustered by their profile variables. It shows that, as appended, all the respondents have outstanding performance but the highest mean are the females, age 41 and above, Accountant I, division school, and doctoral degree. However, those who attended trainings on Accounting and Auditing Services, Finance Management and Budget Related – Records and Files Management – Human Resources

and Personnel Management – Administrative and Technical Support – Organization Support, and Records and Files Management - Human Resources and Personnel Management - Administrative and Technical Support – Coordination, Communication and – Organizational Support have very satisfactory performance, while the others are of outstanding performance.

It has been revealed that performance and position or designation are highly significant in the comparison of the performance of the non-teaching personnel and their profile variables. This implies that performance is highly attributed on their position or designation. As significantly established and discussed earlier, position or designation affects the performance of employees. To put it up, when an employee seeks to upgrade in his or her professional dealings to upgrade a position or designation, then performance is also a byproduct not just for the employee for also for the organization as a whole.

In considering age as a factor in the performance level of administrative employees, Apolonio (2017) claimed that age gaps and differences affect the productivity levels and efficiency of employees in an organization as it could expand or lower the employees' amount of efficient production.

In addition, A related study by Osborne (2016) found that sex is a factor in employees' output efficiency and performance level, claiming that female employees are more output-efficient in a public institution or an office with public responsibilities. This point was also affirmed in the study of Manansala (2004), claiming that sex significantly influences employees' level of output efficiency and level of performance. In a parallel study by Cubukcu and Donmez (2011), it was found that female employees produce more work than male employees in an organization. In addition, they manifested a higher level of output efficiency as they are more involved in more senses development that help or aid their perception and attitude toward work and the working environment or workweek scheme.

This finding was supported by several studies that reveal the likelihood of performance of employees with higher and better working positions notwithstanding the type of work set up or working schedule. According to Bakker & Demerouti (2017), performance is a positive, fulfilling, and work-related state of mind that is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption. The vigor is characterized by high levels of energy and mental resilience, vitality, and flexibility during work, and being determined even in the face of difficulties during work. Dedication is the state in which an individual shows complete enthusiasm and involvement for work, and there is a practical effort, passion, respect, and challenging task. Absorption means that an individual is deeply focused and determined, engrossed in working, while time moves rapidly.

The result was confirmed in the study of Littky (2004) stating that education level directly affects employees' success and level of performance in any type or kind of workweek schedule. It is further revealed that when the employee, who is usually a degree holder, makes efforts to educate and further enhance oneself personally and professionally, there is more likely a positive reinforcement of educational goals due to

the employee's educational attainment. The level of education could also be determinative of employees' success in any organization, workstation, or organization.

According to Schaufeli (2011) at the beginning of the 21st century, employee performance emerged as a concept with the convergence of human capital economic theory and increasing scientific interest in positive psychology. From this convergence, interest in employee psychology materialized because organizations needed to consider how to efficiently manage their human capital expenditure while simultaneously increasing their organizational performance. However, according to Johnstone (2020), the human capital equation of producing more output with fewer employees translates into organizations having no choice but to try to engage not only the body but also the mind and the soul of every employee.

Finally, as concluded by Chievenato (2009) in the comparison between employees' performance and their attended relevant trainings and continuing professional development, these factors are contributory aspects of significant changes and development in the professional dealings of the employee. Training and development of people implies the transformation of individuals in their values, attitudes, behaviors, and skills to serve organizational change and not only provide them with information so that they learn new knowledge. So, training is concerned with the efforts made by every organization to enable its employees to develop their skills in the workplace including the knowledge, skills, and behaviors that are fundamental to successful performance.

For Cunha et al. (2009), the comparison between training of non-teaching staff and development and other measures of training and human resource assessment (such as salary, potential and performance evaluation, harmonization of individual praxis with organizational/institutional strategy) is closely related to planning practices that are aimed at individual collaborators and that positively affect outcomes in terms of performance and service delivery. As for other comments, the changes currently occurring require new skills, knowledge, and abilities from all people and training involves the possibility that each of them can contribute effectively to the organization to proactively adapt to these changes, ensuring that only the continuity of the process and its dynamics, but an increase in its capacity to meet social demands. The idea of training includes the transfer of knowledge, the standard is represented by actions on individual performance, which aim to improve team performance. So, training non-teaching staff in basic education institutions to increase work creativity, knowledge, and skills in the field of administration in supporting the teaching and learning process, performance, and the provision of public services.

Relationship between the Level of Competence and Performance of the Non-Teaching Personnel

Table 46. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Competence and Performance of the Non-Teaching Personnel

Variables	Probability of r	Remarks
Self-Management and Performance	0.5192	Not Significant

Professionalism and Ethics and Performance	0.3352	Not Significant
Result Focus and Performance	0.2332	Not Significant
Teamwork and Performance	0.0833	Not Significant
Service Orientation and Performance	0.1456	Not Significant
Innovation and Performance	0.4118	Not Significant

Table 46 discloses the results of the test of a significant relationship between the level of competence and performance of the non-teaching personnel.

The results reveal that the probability values of r are greater than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. Thus, there is no significant relationship between the level of competence and performance of the non-teaching personnel. It implies that the competence level of the non-teaching personnel on self-management, professionalism and ethics, result focus, teamwork, service orientation, and innovation do not significantly affect their performance. It states further that the performance of the non-teaching personnel does not depend on their competence level in the said six areas.

In the study, Lingam (2002), cited that one of the critical factors that positively affects employees' performance and efficacy as productive employees is the level of training engagements, continuing education, and level of competencies such as enrollment to higher education, post-graduate studies, trainings relevant to job descriptions and other relatively significant trainings prescribed by their agencies, employers, or institutional management of the human resources division office. Also, Muwonge et al. (2002) found that strong social support from school administrators and supervisors from the school, and good resource management, are cited to be a few factors that contribute to the development of employees to strive and seek continuing education relevant to their job description.

This was supported by Khan et.al (2019) stating that employee effectiveness is essential in developing human resources because if the training is ineffective, it will not be helpful. Training is effective and it can enjoy the results for the trainees and the organization. In organizations that provide services at the forefront, educational organizations such as universities, schools, and others must use personnel who can meet specific standards. Various studies show that training is the best way to get the skills employees need.

Further, as emphasized by Khan (2019), the improved quality of work is a key outcome that can be expected from training initiatives. However, it is worth mentioning that such practices are increasingly focused and personalized. They seek to meet specific demands in a particular field or professional profile, accelerate their assimilation, and improve work outcomes. However, this quality is reflected not only in public services but also in the level of professional trust. Each work program must address all problems in public administration, and the absence of certain competencies, that is, contribute to developing new skills, knowledge, and attitudes in a professional or work team.

The foregoing results discussed are comparative analyses of the association between the level of competence and performance of employees in the Schools Division

Office of the City of Ilagan. Hannah as cited by Cody (2011) pointed out, that competencies are contributory factors in the success or failure of employees in the fields of work development and productivity as employees. Hence, it is indispensable for administrators and supervisors to ensure that training engagements, continuing education, and other relevant learning or educational opportunities are maximized to improve personal efficacy and skills development.

However, contrary to these claims and assertions, the cited indicators of the level of competence of non-teaching employees in the education sector which include Self-Management, Professionalism and Ethics, Result Focus, Teamwork, Service Orientation, and Innovation signify that these indicators of the level of competence of administrative employees do not affect their performance in an organization specifically to the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan. As established by Landale (2020), there are several sources of employees' productivity and performance attribution which could be both personal and professional. In the personal aspect, there is a huge relativity of positive connection between stability in the socio-economic status of employees. For instance, when employees are well-stationed in their personal lives, optimistic results could prosper in their workstations. Hence, performance and productivity of employees are not always cited in their professional attributions which are centered on organizational and institutional aspects including teamwork, result focus, service orientation, and work innovations. Aside from professional training, non-teaching employees and administrative employees could be further developed by considering aspects of their working conditions. However, training development in a holistic approach contributes meaningfully to the improvement of employees in the administrative, financial, and technical aspects of administrative work.

Conclusions

Considering the above results, the study concludes that the level of competence of the non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan is overall high which indicates that they are highly competent in terms of Self-Management, Professionalism and Ethics, Result Focus, Teamwork, Service Orientation, and Innovation. This means that the personal attributes of the employees are factors towards their competence.

In their level of performance, most of the respondents performed outstanding. It is also concluded that the performance of non-teaching personnel varies according to their profile variables. This further implies that they perform differently according to their personal and professional dealings. However, some respondents were rated below outstanding performance.

Hence, in this study, there is a need to develop and devise a sustainable upskilling program to maintain the status quo and to relatively answer the problem of sustainability experienced by non-teaching personnel about their competence and performance as employees of the Department of Education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are considered to formulate and devise proper and appropriate mechanisms to further improve the bounds of the study:

1. Since it was found that non-teaching personnel of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan are highly competent, an appraisal system should be developed to reinforce good working practices and management capabilities to enforce the sustainability of results.
2. Since the number of relevant trainings attended significantly caused a difference in the non-teaching personnel's level of competence and performance, administrative employees must be sent and actively participate in more trainings related to the indicators of the competence of non-teaching personnel.
3. Development of sustainability and enhancement of an upskilling program should be formulated and developed based on the performance of the administrative employees.
4. Non-teaching employees may devise, craft, customize, and implement individual personal and professional developmental goals targeting the competencies and performance key indicators as non-teaching personnel that would foresee engagements for the next three to five years.
5. Non-teaching personnel who performed excellently in their Individual/Office Performance Commitment Review Form with an Outstanding Rating are recommended for merit increase or additional enumeration as indicated in the Result Based Performance Management System.
6. Administrative Aide employees must maintain and organize the grounds and facilities of the Schools Division Office of the City of Ilagan.
7. Finally, an Upskilling Program must be developed, crafted, implemented, and monitored as a response to the results and findings in the study that highlighted the levels of performance and competence of the employees.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares that this research was conducted with strict adherence to ethical guidelines. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before their involvement in the study, ensuring they were fully aware of the research objectives, procedures, and potential risks. Respondents were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. The anonymity of all participants was maintained throughout the research process, and their well-being was safeguarded. No conflict of interest exists in the conduct of this study. The authors have strictly avoided plagiarism, ensuring that all sources are properly cited and acknowledged. Furthermore,

the interpretation of the findings was conducted without bias, and the results were used solely for research purposes.

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